

Studies on equilibrium constants of binary and ternary complexes of 3-hydroxyquinazolin-2,4(3H)-dione with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} at different temperatures

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Abstract : The stability constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 binary M^{II}-HQDO and ternary [M^{II}-HQDO-A] chelates [where M^{II} = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}; HQDO = 3-hydroxyquinazolin-2,4(3H)-dione, A = glycine (gly), α -alanine (ala), proline (pro), histidine (hist), iminodiacetic acid (IMDA), nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and ethylenediamine (en)] have been determined pH-metrically in 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium at 20, 30 and 40 °C and $I = 0.1 M$ KNO₃. The order of formation constants of binary as well as ternary chelates are Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}. The formation of binary complexes are more favourable over ternary complexes. The thermodynamic parameters were evaluated.

Keywords : Ternary complex, binary complex, equilibrium constants, stability constants.

Cyclic hydroxamic acids are known for biological activity^{1,2}, such as anti-helmintic agents, anti-microbial, bactericidal, analgesic, hypnotic, anti-convulsant, anti-inflammatory, CNS depressants and also have gained significant importance as anti-pyretic, anti-allergic, anti-ulcer, anti-cancer, anti-tumor, anti-HIV drugs. Besides these also act as a good chelating agents. Survey of literature reveals that little work has been done on chelating tendencies of these compounds. The formation of binary and ternary metal complexes of 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl quinazolin-4-one³, 2-(*o*-carboxy phenyl)-3-hydroxy-4(3H)-quinazolinone⁴, 3-hydroxy-2-chloromethyl quinazolin-4-one⁵ with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} have been determined pH-metrically at different temperatures of 20, 30 and 40 °C at 0.1 M ionic strength. In the present investigation the formation constants of binary and mixed ligand complexes of 3-hydroxy-quinazolin-2,4(3H)-dione with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in the presence of glycine (gly), α -alanine (ala), proline (pro), histidine (hist), iminodiacetic acid (IMDA), nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and ethylenediamine (en) have been determined pH-metrically at different temperatures of 20, 30 and 40 °C. The thermodynamic parameters were also evaluated.

Results and discussion

Binary systems :

The pK_a value for HQDO was determined pH-metrically for the first time. The \bar{n}_H values (0.1–1.0) for HQDO indicating the liberation of one proton, which is due to the dissociation of proton from hydroxamic group as shown below.

\bar{n}_H values (0.1 < \bar{n} < 1.9) obtained for M^{II}-HQDO system indicate the formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in solution. The acid dissociation constants and binary formation constants so obtained are presented in Table 1. It was established that the carbonyl oxygen and -OH groups are participating in bonding with the metal ion. The releasing of protons in the pH range of above 3 in the present investigation indicates that -OH group is participating in bonding with the metal ion. From these

Table 1. Stability constants of binary complexes of HQDO with M^{II} ions at different temperatures and 0.1 M ionic strength in 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium

Metal ion	Stability constants	Different temperatures		
		20 °C	30 °C	40 °C
H ⁺	pK _a	5.39	5.25	5.09
Co ^{II}	log K ₁	4.85	4.66	4.46
	log K ₂	2.96	2.85	2.7
Ni ^{II}	log K ₁	5.26	5.05	4.85
	log K ₂	2.99	2.86	2.71
Cu ^{II}	log K ₁	5.29	5.11	4.96
	log K ₂	4.3	4.14	3.95
Zn ^{II}	log K ₁	5.17	5.01	4.81
	log K ₂	3.71	3.55	3.37

studies it was established that these ligands act as O-O donors. The order of formation constants of metal chelates under investigation are Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} which is in conformity with the Irving-William natural order of stabilities³. The formation of various metal ligand species in solution with the variation of pH has been calculated by using the computer program BEST⁷. Binary pH titration curves of M^{II}-HQDO are given in the Fig. 1. The acid dissociation constants and the log K values of gly, ala, pro, hist, bipy, IMDA, NTA and en have been determined under similar experimental conditions and presented in Table 2.

Ternary complexes :

In the formation of ternary complexes [M^{II}-HQDO-A] HQDO coordinated with metal ions [where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}, A = gly, ala, pro, en] in stepwise manner. The mixed ligand curves of [M^{II}-HQDO-A] closely follow the 1 : 1 M^{II}-HQDO curves in the lower pH region, until the protons of HQDO were neutralised, indicating that the binary [M^{II}-HQDO] complexes predominate in this region. Above this region the divergence of the ternary curve from those of binary M^{II}-HQDO systems reveals the formation of ternary complexes of the type [M^{II}-HQDO-A] in stepwise equilibria. Here, HQDO acts as a primary ligand. Such a stepwise formation of ternary complex is confirmed from the distribution diagram (Fig. 2), that in the lower pH range the major species are the free metal ion and the [M-HQDO] species, whereas in the higher pH range the major species are [M^{II}-HQDO] and [M^{II}-HQDO-A].

In the case of A (where A = IMDA, NTA, bipy and hist) HQDO coordinated with metal ions in simultaneous manner. The mixed ligand curves of [M^{II}-A-HQDO] nei-

Fig. 1. Binary pH titration curves of transition metal ions with HQDO.

Table 2. Acid dissociation constants and log K₁ values

I = 0.1 M KNO₃, medium : 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol, temp. = 303 K

	pK _{a1}	pK _{a2}	log K ₁			
			Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
gly	9.57	2.36	4.64	5.78	8.15	5.30
ala	9.69	2.30	4.31	5.40	8.13	5.60
pro	10.36	2.40	5.10	5.95	8.83	5.65
hist	9.08	6.07	6.90	8.67	10.2	6.55
bipy	4.48	-	5.72	6.12	8.39	5.20
IMDA	3.34	9.21	6.93	8.12	10.58	7.21
NTA	3.70	10.00	3.65	4.95	5.44	10.44
en	6.61	9.50	6.26	6.96	10.46	5.81

ther followed [M-HQDO] binary curve nor [M-A] binary titration curves. As a representative case, Ni^{II}-bipy-HQDO titration curves are given in the Fig. 3. The equilibria involved in the ternary complex formation of the type [M^{II}-A-HQDO] can be represented by the following equation (charges are omitted for the sake of clarity).

(where A = IMDA, NTA, hist and bipy)

It is observed from the distribution diagram that the $[M^{II}-A-HQDO]$ species predominates in the entire pH range over $[M^{II}-A]$ and $[M^{II}-HQDO]$ which confirms the formation of complexes simultaneously.

Fig. 2. Distribution diagram of Cu^{II} -ala-HQDO (1 : 1 : 1).

The stability constant of ternary complexes so obtained are presented in Table 3. The order of stability of $[M^{II}-A-HQDO]$ ternary complexes with respect to secondary ligands A are pro > gly > ala > en. The trends in the case of secondary ligands are almost all in conformity with the basicity sequence of the ligands under investigation. gly forms more stable complex than ala because of the absence of any alkyl side chain, which may produce an unfavorable steric effect in other amino acids studied⁸. Perusal of $\log K^9$ data reveals that ternary chelates formed by en are less stable than those of gly, ala, pro. Probably, this may be due to the fact that in the case

Fig. 3. pH titration curves of Ni^{II} -HQDO-bipy ternary complexes in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio.

of en the interaction occurs between neutral en and unipositive $[M-HQDO]^+$ primary species. In case of amino acids, the interaction is between uninegative amino acid A^- and unipositive $[M-HQDO]^+$ primary species. Therefore the attraction between en and $[M-HQDO]^+$ is less than the attraction between amino acid A^- and $[M-HQDO]^+$. Thus the stability of ternary complexes of en is less stable than those of gly, ala, pro. $\Delta \log K^9$ data also reveals that ternary complexes formed by gly are more favorable than ala which is reversal to their basicity values. Methyl group on ala may be responsible for destabilization of its ternary complexes. In the present investigation the order of stabilities of $[M-A-HQDO]$ ternary complexes formed in simultaneous equilibria, is as follows :

The relative order of stabilities with respect to metal ions

Table 3. Stability constants of ternary metal complexes of M^{II} ions with HQDO in presence of other chelating agents

Temp. = 303 K, $I = 0.1 M KNO_3$, medium : 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol	gly		ala		pro		en		IMDA		NTA		bipy		hist	
	$\log K_{MLA}^M$	$\Delta \log K$	$\log K_{MLA}^M$	$\Delta \log K$	$\log K_{MLA}^M$	$\Delta \log K$	K_{MLA}^M	$\Delta \log K$								
HQDO																
Co^{II}	4.46	-0.26	4.56	0.17	5.09	-0.11	5.07	-1.31	8.25	-4.18	7.05	-1.27	9.34	-0.52	10.27	-4.89
Ni^{II}	4.90	-0.95	4.69	-0.78	5.34	-0.71	5.47	-1.62	9.57	-4.3	8.52	-1.49	9.75	-0.85	9.24	-5.19
Cu^{II}	6.55	-1.49	6.69	-1.43	7.47	-1.41	7.02	-3.54	12.62	-3.96	9.21	-6.35	10.14	-2.72	11.14	-4.77
Zn^{II}	5.44	-0.01	5.53	-0.19	6.36	0.53	5.29	-0.68	8.70	-4.28	7.93	-2.52	9.14	-0.56	7.74	-4.42

in all the HQDO ternary complex systems [$Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$] is in agreement with the Irving-William natural order of stability. The extent of favoured formation of the ternary complexes can be inferred from $\Delta \log K$ values. The negative $\Delta \log K$ values reveal that the formation of ternary complexes are not favoured over that of binary complexes.

Effect of temperature :

In the present study, the complexation equilibria of HQDO were studied with the transition metal ions Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} at three different temperatures 20, 30 and 40 °C at constant ionic strength of 0.1 M KNO_3 . The formation constant data of binary metal complexes [M^{II} -HQDO] are presented in Table 1. The stability constants data obtained at different temperatures has been used in the evaluation of thermodynamic parameters^{10,11} accompanying the formation of metal complexes.

The ΔH values thus obtained were refined by using the algebraic equation. The values of overall change in the free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and the entropy (ΔS) for the complexation reactions of HQDO with the transition metal ions are reported in the Table 4. The data shows that the acid dissociation constants pK_a of the ligand and their stability constants with metal ions decreases with the increase in the temperature, indicating that the formation equilibria are exothermic in nature. This is also evident from the negative values of the enthalpy (ΔH). The negative values of free energy (ΔG) and the positive values of entropy (ΔS) indicate that these factors are major driving force for the spontaneity of the binary chelates. The results obtained in the present cases suggested that the metal-ligand bonds are fairly strong as evidenced by their negative enthalpy changes.

The formation constants of the ternary complexes [M-A-HQDO] (where $M = Cu^{II}$ and Ni^{II} , $A = gly, ala, pro, hist, bipy, en, IMDA$ and NTA) were evaluated at 20, 30 and 40 °C at 0.1 M ionic strength and presented in Table 5. The thermodynamic parameters enthalpy (ΔH), entropy (ΔS) and free energy (ΔG) were calculated and presented in Table 6.

The formation constants of all the systems were found to decrease with increase in temperature, indicating that the reactions are exothermic in nature and enthalpy favored. The negative ΔH and ΔG values indicate that these factors are responsible for the spontaneity of the reaction in all the cases. The positive values of entropy (ΔS) indicate that the complexation reactions are also favored by entropy. The more positive values of (ΔS) for the ternary systems, compared to binary systems indicate that the

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal chelates of HQDO

Temp. = 30 °C, *I* = 0.1 M KNO₃, medium : 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol

Metal ion	1 : 1 Complex			1 : 2 Complex		
	-Δ <i>G</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	-Δ <i>H</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>S</i> kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	-Δ <i>G</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	-Δ <i>H</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	-Δ <i>S</i> kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Co ^{II}	926.77	705.11	174.84	630.68	548.56	64.77
Ni ^{II}	975.17	718.86	202.17	632.79	546.67	67.93
Cu ^{II}	982.28	610.81	293.01	855.52	669.05	147.09
Zn ^{II}	970.38	554.67	327.90	762.93	523.06	599.36

Table 5. Formation constants of M^{II}-A-HQDO ternary complexes at 0.1 M KNO₃ and at different temperatures

I = 0.1 M KNO₃, medium : 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol, temp. = 303 K

A	Cu ^{II} -A-HQDO			Ni ^{II} -A-HQDO		
	20 °C	30 °C	40 °C	20 °C	30 °C	40 °C
gly	6.81	6.66	6.5	4.99	4.83	4.66
ala	6.89	6.70	6.53	4.77	4.62	4.46
pro	7.59	7.42	7.24	5.39	5.24	5.08
hist	10.94	10.54	10.31	8.92	8.53	8.13
en	7.13	6.92	6.72	5.55	5.34	5.12
IMDA	12.17	11.73	11.26	9.22	8.87	8.41
NTA	9.64	9.20	8.79	8.99	8.51	8.02

formations of ternary complexes are more favored by entropy.

Experimental

HQDO is prepared and purified by the method of Kuniyoshi Tanaka *et al.*¹². The solution of the HQDO was prepared in distilled ethanol¹³ since solubility is low in water. The metal solutions were prepared by dissolving metal nitrate of A.R. grade (E. Merck) in double-

distilled water and standardized by EDTA¹⁴. Potassium hydroxide (B.D.H.) and HNO₃ (E. Merck) solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and standardized by the usual methods. The other reagents gly (E. Merck), ala, pro, hist, IMDA, NTA, en (Sigma), bipy, EDTA, KNO₃ (B.D.H.) of A.R. grade were used and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Proton-ligand, metal-ligand formation constants of binary systems were determined pH-metrically by Irving-Rossotti^{15,16} titration technique. The metal-ligand ratio was maintained at 1 : 5. The ligand concentration was maintained at 2.00 × 10⁻³ M and the metal ion concentration was maintained at 4.00 × 10⁻⁴ M. The total volume was maintained at 50 mL. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M by adding requisite amount of potassium nitrate in binary and ternary titrations. The stability constants were calculated by Irving and Rossotti method and further refined by using computer program PKAS¹⁷ and BEST¹⁸.

For the determination of stability constants of ternary or mixed ligand complexes, the molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 (metal ion, ligand A and ligand L) was maintained and the total volume of solution is kept at 50 mL. The con-

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters for the formation of ternary metal complexes of HQDO

Temp. = 30 °C, *I* = 0.1 M KNO₃, medium : 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol

Secondary ligand	HQDO-Cu ^{II}			HQDO-Ni ^{II}		
	-Δ <i>G</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	-Δ <i>H</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>S</i> kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	-Δ <i>G</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	-Δ <i>H</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	-Δ <i>S</i> kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
gly	1141.81	392.98	590.66	948.35	575.01	294.48
ala	1145.42	493.39	514.31	921.58	563.75	282.25
pro	1206.88	399.68	636.70	997.41	497.98	393.94
hist	1418.25	657.21	600.29	1290.83	788.80	395.99
en	1182.88	-527.47	1349.09	1008.79	680.57	258.90
IMDA	1504.84	-649.73	1699.48	1314.37	682.83	498.15
NTA	1364.50	-824.28	1726.47	1289.42	968.14	253.42

concentrations of both the ligands and metal ion were maintained at $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$. All the solutions were titrated against 0.1 M potassium hydroxide.

The formation constants of ternary systems were determined by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santhappa^{19,20} and further refined by BEST¹⁸ and SCOGS²¹ computer programmes. 10% of aqueous-ethanol medium is maintained in all the titrations since the solubility of HQDO is low in pure water. pH meter readings in 10% (v/v) ethanol-water were corrected by the method of Van Uitert and Haas²². The distribution of various species as a function of pH has been calculated by using the computer program BEST¹⁸. The $\Delta \log K^9$ values (difference between the stabilities of ternary and corresponding binary complexes) were evaluated.

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